

COMPANY IN THE EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT OF THE ROLE OF MARKETING AND PROSPECTS FOR APPLYING ITS PRINCIPLES

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Abstract. *This article discusses the use of a marketing approach in managing a company, justifying the feasibility and necessity of the production of a specific product based on the determination of existing or potential demand, operational management of all company activities, including various stages of the production process, after-sales service, expansion and promotion of product sales. is considered to ensure orientation.*

Keywords: *company, production, activity, operational management, promotion, service.*

INTRODUCTION. The economic reforms carried out in our country open the door to wide opportunities for production enterprises. As a result of the benefits and preferences given to them, the increase of funds at the disposal of enterprises, the introduction of new forces and the increase of the welfare of the population serve. It is certainly gratifying to see such positive changes in our economy and the economic activity of the country. However, today we all know well that the market economy is an economic system that operates within the framework of the influence of a complex of competition and so-called struggles. In this system, some enterprises cooperate with each other, and similar enterprises are in constant competition. In their economic activities, they always meet the needs of the times,

Analysis of literature on the topic. Based on foreign experiences, it should be noted that the competitiveness of the enterprise in the market is determined by the effectiveness of its market-oriented policy. Many economists have been engaged in the development of marketing principles and their practical application, including F. Kotler, M. Porter, D. Evans, I. Ansoff, M. Berman, M. Golubkov, P. Samuelson, D. .We can include famous scientists like Marshall.

It is necessary to acknowledge the scientists who made a great contribution to the development of the theory of marketing, while the research carried out in the field of marketing in our country for many years was based on national characteristics. R. Ibragimov to them. Y. Abdullaev, A. Saliev, M. Sharifkhojaev, D. Rakhimova, SH. Ergashkhodjaeva and others can be included.

Marketing management is the analysis, planning, implementation and control of activities aimed at establishing, strengthening and maintaining profitable exchanges with target customers in order to achieve certain objectives of the organization, such as increasing profits, increasing sales, increasing market share, etc. There are two levels of marketing management: strategic and tactical. The strategic level of marketing management (marketing strategy) is the long-term coordination of the company's capabilities with the market situation, that is, the coordination of the internal and external environment of the company's activities.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results. For the purpose of research company effective management includes identifying ways to apply marketing principles.

In order to achieve this goal, the following tasks were solved in the research:

- Importance of marketing principles in modern management theory;
- Revealing the content of the analytical function in marketing activities;
- Determining the main directions and indicators of marketing analysis;
- Analyzing the marketing activity of the selected enterprise;
- Development of ways to improve marketing analysis in production enterprises.

Marketing strategy is often confused with a company's business development goals. However, unlike goals, a marketing strategy is a plan to achieve these goals, and it should reflect all elements of marketing, financial resources, and production capabilities. The most common marketing strategies:

- improvement of the organizational structure of the company;
- organizing access to new product markets;
- development and marketing of new products;
- entering new markets by establishing joint ventures;
- cooperation of activities with companies with experience of successful operation in interested markets.

Marketing and management has an international character, and with the wide introduction of information technologies in management, the role of marketing increases. Competition includes not only goods and their technologies, but also types of management and their elements: planning systems, advertising, information technology, communication systems, motivation, incentives and professionalism of employees.

The formation of the marketing management system in the enterprise depends on the influence of the macro environment, the stability of the micro environment and the optimal development of the internal environment of the enterprise. Marketing management strategy depends on political instability, unpredictable market and financial environment, rise or fall of competitive positions, mission choice and customer interactions. Marketing management influences the level, timing, and nature of demand in such a way that it helps achieve the firm's goals.

Marketing is an important part of the enterprise management system. Marketing shows the direction of the company's development and enables the successful implementation of marketing tools. F. Kotler believes that the use of marketing in management is related to the fact that it is aimed at solving certain management problems, in particular:

- justifying the expediency and necessity of the production of a certain product based on the determination of existing or potential demand;
- organization of scientific-research works that satisfy the needs of consumers;
- production and financial organization planning;
- formation and improvement of product marketing system;
- ensure that all the company's activities, including operational management of various stages of the production process, after-sales service, are oriented towards the expansion and promotion of product sales.

Using a marketing approach in managing a company requires a certain organizational structure, which should include marketing services. The company's activity is determined by the

specific characteristics of its structure and size, as well as its scope of activity and the type of market served.

In modern society, both in the country and abroad, against the background of the complex financial and economic situation, there is a sharp change in consumer demand, a change in the scale of production, and the genesis of various market factors. These conditions require the company to respond adequately by improving not only its production and market activities, but also its management mechanism. In relation to the above, marketing planning should be flexible and dynamic; its structural elements - marketing plans are elastic only when they can change their organizational forms under the influence of internal and external factors. However, if the ability to change is built directly into the structure,

In the conditions of the current turbulent development of the international market, the choice of marketing management strategy is related to the characteristics of regional markets, the level of activity of small, medium and large businesses, and the payment capacity of the population in the regions. The marketing strategy in new markets used by Japanese firms is of great interest, which allows them to gain a foothold in the markets of countries that do not have national production of this product, and then gain experience and enter the markets of other countries ("laser beam strategy"). Thus, in order to enter the markets of Western European countries with their cars, Japanese automobile companies initially operated only in Finland, Norway, Denmark and Ireland for several years. And after gaining a strong positive reputation there, they began to master the more sophisticated markets of the Netherlands, Switzerland, Sweden, Austria, Belgium. The third step was to enter the markets of Great Britain, Italy, Germany and France - countries with a powerful automobile industry. It is also worth noting the very long-term sequence characteristic of the activity of Japanese industrialists: starting with the export of the largest, cheapest cars (and, accordingly, very quickly meeting the demands of customers), creating the image of "Japan is excellent quality", this car companies gradually began to work in the markets of more expensive cars (but not the most prestigious), trucks and special cars, as well as in the countries where they sent previously assembled cars, later they move on to building car assembly plants. Germany and France are countries with strong automotive industries.

An interesting strategy is "blue oceans", which allows companies to independently choose the field of activity, new products and new customers, away from the struggle for trade markets. In the conditions of the current turbulent development of the international market, the choice of marketing management strategy is related to the characteristics of regional markets, the level of activity of small, medium and large businesses, and the payment capacity of the population in the regions.

In the process of operational planning, marketing programs and budgets that take into account the company's current goals for the next period, guidelines for all components of the company are developed. A marketing program or a program of marketing activities makes it possible to conduct a strategic policy, avoid important economic and social shocks, achieve development stability and have a long-term positive impact. Along with the marketing program, one of the main components of marketing planning is the marketing budget. The marketing budget is a balanced system of income and expenses for marketing, its development is the leading element of financial planning of the company's activities. The budget is developed for a period of one year or more,

Marketing costs are formed in two main ways. The first is related to percentage of revenue or profit. The second approach means that the main factors for calculating the marketing budget should be the goals and objectives of the company at this stage of development. A variation of the goal-oriented approach is sometimes called competitive marketing budgeting. A marketing budget is a budget related to advertising and other activities aimed at attracting consumers. This also includes marketing research, branding and more. However, marketing costs also include marketing product development costs, affiliate bonuses and discounts. The exact list of marketing cost items is determined by the business processes and the location of the control centers of these items. For example, if the marketing department and the sales department in a company are different departments with different budgets, then the same bonuses to partners may not be included in the marketing budget, but may be included in the sales department budget. Conversely, if sales and marketing are structurally owned by the same unit, the budget may be the same. The distribution of marketing expenses by main items is presented in Table 1. but may be included in the sales department budget. Conversely, if sales and marketing are structurally owned by the same unit, the budget may be the same. The distribution of marketing expenses by main items is presented in Table 1. but may be included in the sales department budget. Conversely, if sales and marketing are structurally owned by the same unit, the budget may be the same. The distribution of marketing expenses by main items is presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Distribution of marketing expenses by main items

	Expenses	Coefficient
	Traditional advertising	0.7
	Sales promotion	0.16
	Direct Marketing	0.08
	Marketing research	0.06

In marketing you can use the analogy method to estimate the level of costs required for it , for example, in the United States, the costs of developing and marketing a new product are distributed as follows: 3-6% of the estimated costs are allocated to fundamental research, and 7-8% to practical development. , 7-8% for the preparation of technological equipment and, if necessary, for the construction of new enterprises - 40-60%, for the establishment of mass production - 5-16%, for the organization of sales - 10-27%. Advertising costs vary depending on the product sold: meat products require 0.6% to 10% of sales, pharmaceuticals and cosmetics 15%, durable goods 1-5% of sales, industrial goods - 1-2%. If we relate the cost of advertising to the amount of profit, as a rule, they are above 15%, and for many firms they are in the range of 30-42% with a stable position in the market, and sometimes reach 45.0% when entering a new market. The natural desire of any business leader to reduce marketing costs must be tempered by the increasingly expensive nature of marketing in today's world.

The efficiency of marketing in management allows to achieve minimum costs and maximum results based on the tasks set in the company's activities and the expected final results. The level of quality in the development of the marketing program and budget, in connection with the above, is one of the elements that determine the effectiveness of enterprise management.

Thus, marketing is one of the most important management functions that allows not only the implementation of purely marketing goals and objectives, but also the coordination of the company's activities to ensure the achievement of planned production indicators. In companies,

appropriate departments should be created to carry out the management function of marketing. The implementation of marketing in the management of the organization should be based on a comprehensive study of the conditions of its operating environment, its determination serves to achieve the main goal of the company, such as directing all the company's activities to market requirements, ensuring its flexibility in the foreign market.

Conclusions and suggestions

In summary, We offer the following methods of applying brand management methods in enterprise management:

1. Market research. Market research is a crucial step in developing effective marketing management techniques. Businesses can collect information about customer needs, preferences and behavior to inform their marketing strategies and product development. This may include identifying specific sectors, regions, or demographics that are most likely to purchase their products.

2. Digital marketing. Digital marketing is very necessary in today's digital age. Businesses can develop a strong online presence through a website, social media, and other digital channels to reach and connect with customers. This includes creating high-quality content such as tutorials, product guides and industry news that provide value to customers and position the business as a leader in the industry.

3. Participation in industrial events. Attending industry events such as trade shows is an effective way to showcase products, make connections and generate leads. It can also provide valuable networking opportunities and insight into the latest trends and innovations in the market.

4. Brand identity. Developing a strong brand identity is also essential to differentiate products from competitors and resonate with target audiences. Creating a consistent and memorable brand identity can help build brand awareness and customer loyalty over time.

5. Special products. Offering specialized products and services can meet unique customer needs and build loyalty. This may involve working with customers to develop custom products that meet their specific needs and preferences.

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